

Police and National Guard Helping the Community on the COVID 19 Crises

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Public security is a systemic and optimized process that involves a set of public and community actions, aimed at ensuring the protection of the individual and the community and the application of justice in the punishment, recovery and treatment of those who violate the law, guaranteeing rights and citizenship at all.

A systemic process because it involves, in the same scenario, a set of knowledge and tools of competence of the constituted powers and within the reach of the organized community, interacting and sharing common vision, commitments and objectives; and optimized because it depends on quick decisions and immediate results.

The citizen police or National Guard attuned and supported by the community's wishes, will only succeed if they are focused on the recovery of those who arrest them, otherwise they will simply be a policeman who forms a criminal, that is, they will recruit criminals, and they will still marginalize more.

It is necessary to include, in this analysis, the entire communication system between enforcement forces and communities police. This is the task that needs to be developed.

What model does society want? Is it a "hard line" police? Is it a "tough" judiciary with high penalties? Is it a maximum security prison? In relation to children and adolescents, also measures to strengthen repressive actions?

The citizen asks the following question: what is the role of the police at a time when employment, family and school are in crisis?

That is to say, the institutions of informal social control that were functioning 51 years ago are in crisis: can the police today only follow the model of a police, say, zero tolerance type? Or is it possible to think, in a country like most of the European countries another type of policing, another police technique, another type of police work?

The central issue is the historical perception of the phenomenon of collective insecurity (not only by criminals but also but health, financial crisis that reflects also in an criminal activity increase.

A society, which does not have a deep and qualified debate on the topic, at the same time that the government itself lacks this debate, as demonstrated by the scarcity of

public policies and the manifestations of the authorities, which bring a partial view of this phenomenon, linked only to one of the components of this system, that is, Justice and the Police.

The question of insecurity grows due to the understanding that Justice and the Police have a problem and, from there, the entire system is required to find a solution to the question of the functioning of Justice and the Police.

The other public and social sectors that are agents in this system should also be brought into this debate.

Justice and the police, by themselves, are probably the least capable intervention factor to influence changes in the conditions of this phenomenon - public insecurity.

As long as it is not possible to establish another form of perception of this problem, visualizing the largest number of elements that compose it, we will be obtaining the same results of curing an infectious disease, for example, only with pain medication, successively increasing the doses, having, as a consequence, its continuous growth.

When considering the phenomenon as a whole, and not only in limited parts, it will be seen that other models and types of police work will be possible and necessary. It should be noted that several studies have shown that approximately 70% of police interventions are not in the police area, but in the social area, called, here at the assistance and resolution of small conflicts that do not constitute criminal offenses. In the remaining 30%, it will probably be pointed out that the vast majority of interventions correspond to minor offenses.

Currently, the police, in their historical culture, only work with an instrument that is the reaction by force; any conflict and difficulty are resolved by force. It is very difficult to work with situations whose responsibility and guilt are not well defined.

Generally, in any conflict in which the police intervene, the tendency is to criminalize conduct, even if it is out of contempt or disrespect, effecting the solution through the use of force and imprisonment.

Therefore, another question can be asked: in a democratic society, what is the police model to be adopted?

The police issue is a central item on the agenda for the development of a social and sustainable society.

The model really needs to change, as it does not solve and does not help, because the police technique is overcome.

This issue can be addressed, for example, by checking how the police begin to differentiate themselves by the way they understand security, perceiving the intervention only from the perspective of repression

It is necessary to format the security system in Portugal, namely in the various prisms that have been successively the object of public police protests in front of the Parliament over the actual and passed years in protests for their career rights.

A system that establishes responsibilities for government officials, the Judiciary, the Public Prosecutor's Office, the penitentiary body and the police, creating technical and operational links and determining social objectives for prevention, treatment and recovery.

It is understood that the security system must be systemic, fast, a process that involves not only preventive or containment activities: it must have a beginning, which is prevention, and an end, which is to recover and treat the perpetrators of the crime because, otherwise, they will return to crime, and the goal is not to give this opportunity to repeat or entice the crime.

In this system, it is not only the police who are responsible, the Judiciary, the Public Ministry and society in general have to participate in the debate on this topic. It is possible to have a more efficient police, different from the current one, which is divided in half: one works only with the investigative party; another only with the expert part; another only with the ostensive part, cast in their corporatism.

Joint and integration work is necessary.

There are two dimensions to this issue: there is a more preventive police, which expands its field of action, being a police with positive obligations in the community as seen in this current crisis of COVID 19 in the regulation of car traffic and people during the quarantine period.

The police have focused their actions only on negative obligations: arrest, inspect, search, etc.

The Fire Department, for example, fulfils a positive obligation. Prevention is a positive obligation in which the police do not advance, and that is where the problem lies.

Today, the police no longer do due prevention, namely knowing well and communicating with the community where they operate.

It is only limited to criminal prevention, leaving the social aspect to fire-fighters, NGOs and delaying associations and, lastly, to the inhabitants of the same neighbourhood.

Police intervention it is decreasing and not allowing a more interactive role.

The police officer will need to have another view of his object of work, another understanding and, above all, be able and able to be recognizing and understanding social diversity.

It is very difficult to work with situations today, whose responsibility and guilt are not well defined. Currently, the police, in their historical culture, only work with one instrument, which is action-reaction, use force; any conflict must be resolved by force.

It is necessary to invest in a concept of a citizen police, which is a concept that unfolds in a series of dimensions. For example, the issue of community participation, which does not exist in the traditional police, since it was not conceived for this purpose, is a permanent factor in the citizen police, due to the approach of its members to the population and the commitment to public security in the workplace.

Regarding the use of weapons and force, the traditional police act more in the defence and reaction impulse, have a high degree of freedom to act, often without well-defined criteria, while in the citizen police it is necessary to have more accurate practical training. , involving emotions and effects, that determines limited patterns of action that start from principles established by international norms, agreed between countries.

Another factor refers to the distribution of police officers, which, in the traditional police, is done through political interference, the intuition of the leadership, responding to a crisis or in search of financial conditions favourable to police action.

The citizen police, on the other hand, seek to distribute police officers in neighbourhoods, within technical and scientific criteria, establishing territories of responsibility and commitment by the chief to the state of security creating communication and knowing people situations (personal health and financial).

Of course, the number of police officers would increase, as would their integration and professional value with the community.

The legislation, in turn, favours the financial (gratuities) and the rise of the friends of power. For example, all police legislation today favours those close to power. See the case of contracts considered as "extras" such as surveillance.

It is the tacit recognition of the government that is badly paid and legitimizes these extra jobs like sports events surveillance and supermarkets taking care of small pickpockets".

Seeing in a supermarket packed of people a police with a gun (ready to shoot) has no explanation at all – it is risky for all people in the lounge and children are afraid..

Also the citizen police, to be aimed at everyone, with the appreciation of those who perform the core activity, which is something that cannot reverse this process despite the meritorious projects of "Safe School" and "Prevention of Violence"; today, the police officer who is in the end activity earns less, has a more difficult rise and does not have the capacity for political aggregation.

The traditional police also have low salaries, with a large gap between the first and the last level, and the citizen police need to have a reasonable salary, with little distance between hierarchical levels, such as, for example, the traffic police.

All public policies must be directed towards the most vulnerable groups, such as young people, the physically handicapped, women.

In the formation of the police, there should be space to deal with these groups, because, due to their vulnerability, they are the most targeted by the police.

The change begins with the formation of the police and the search for social assistance policies and the generation of jobs and income. This internal reformulation of the police also depends on the movements of society and, therefore, social control is not a control of the police over society, but it must be a control of society over the police. The young man can no longer be treated as a police case.

Why doesn't the policeman treat the young man better? He does not treat it better because the police model is authoritarian. The young person has the spirit of wanting quick, objective answers and has the "criterion of truth by reasoning". For the police officer, used to the "authority criterion", when approaching a young person and he wants to know "why?". This can be understood as an offense. The policeman increasingly needs to move away from the authoritarian model, moving to more action based on argumentation, mediation and conflict resolution.

For some segments of the police, this is mistaken for breaking discipline and hierarchy. Let us hope that the police begin during this quarantine of COVID 19 to visit elderly or needy people, with physical or motor disabilities to just know if everything is okay.

The Police must show individually in each street their presence as a Community Police, taking the example of European countries where the Police is committed to a social service too, complementing its security job such as the United Kingdom, Luxembourg, Belgium, France and Switzerland.

Bless you all citizens that working in the Police or National Guard and don't take this paper as a critic because you do what you are ordered to.